

ANALYSIS OF FACTORS INFLUENCING TIME AND COST OVERRUNS ON CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS IN SOUTH EASTERN NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT: *This study identifies and examines the factors influencing time and cost overruns on construction project in the south eastern Nigeria. The high level of dilapidation and deterioration of roads and other construction infrastructural facilities seen in this zone could be attributed to abysmal performance of construction project management. Survey technique with area and random sampling procedures were employed for the study. The primary data were obtained with the instrument of weighted scaled questionnaires the respondents to the questionnaire are clients, contractors and consultants from five states of south eastern Nigeria. A total of 110 and 42 hypothetical cost and time overruns respectively were identify for analysis. The methods of data analysis were spearman's rank correlation coefficient and Kendall's coefficient of concordance with the hypothesis tested at 5% level of significant so as to determine the degree of agreement amongst the parties. The results of this study have shown that the three parties to a project are in agreement that materials factor and external factor groups have indeed contributed immensely to delays on construction projects, while projects, contractor's responsibilities, consultant's responsibilities, client's responsibilities, professional management, design and documentation, execution, labour and equipment, contractual relationship, government relations, time overruns; cost overrun and all together (time and cost overruns) factors have not greatly influenced delays on construction projects. Based on these results it is recommended that client's, contractor's and consultant's should pay more attention to both material and external factors for there to be effective and efficient delivery on construction projects at the right time and cost.*

Keywords: *Time overrun, Cost overrun, Construction project clients, Contractors, Consultants, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, Kendall's coefficient of concordance.*

INTRODUCTION

The successful execution of construction projects and keeping them within estimated cost and prescribed schedules depend on a methodology that requires sound engineering judgments. Many projects experience extensive delays, exceed initial time schedule and cost estimate to the dislike of clients, contractors and consultants. This problem is more evident in the traditional and public sector type of projects in which contract is awarded to the lowest bidder. This is the contract awarding strategy of the majority of public projects in developing countries including Nigeria. Construction projects in the south eastern Nigeria have suffered serious neglects and setbacks since the Nigeria civil war. In an attempt to address some of the perceived ills in the construction industry marked a milestone in the development of the region. To say the least, the construction industry in south east Nigeria has

continued to undergo through complex changes in the recent times such that clients, contractor's and consultant's now seek to adopt several survival strategies in the face of Keen competition in order to complete projects at the required time and cost.

Factors influencing cost overrun are numerous and therefore require in-depth analysis in order to determine the management of influence and their significant rankings. Previous researchers have attempted to discover reasons for the disparity between the tender sum and the final amount. This study identifies the factors that influence cost overrun. Four factors were identifies from the existing research findings of Morris et al (2006) Kaming et al (2007) and Chimwaso (2006). These are; "design changes", "inadequate planning", "unpredictable weather conditions", and "Fluctuations in the cost of building materials". To broaden the investigation, it was decided to complement the above list of

factors with other factors gleaned from the final account reports. These were compared with the factors from the existing research findings, and final lists of 18 factors were prepared. They were then divided into two groups of seven critical factors and nine other factors, which are usually ignored, but perceived to be of equal significance, (Chimwason 2006).

Similarly, project time overruns adversely influence the performance of construction projects in the South Eastern Zone of Nigeria Kaming et al (2007) define time overrun as the extension of time beyond planned completion date traceable to the contractor. Delays are incidents that impact a project's progress and postpone project activities. Delay causing incidents may include weather delays, unavailability of resources, design delays, etc. In general, project delays occur as a result of project activities that have both external and internal cause and effect relationship, Vidalis et al

$$\text{Cost overrun} = \frac{\text{Final Contract Amount} - \text{Original Contract Amount}}{\text{Original Contract Amount}} \dots\dots\dots 1$$

Choudhry (2004) defined cost overrun as the difference between the original cost estimate of project and actual construction cost on completion of works of a commercial sector construction project.

Construction Project in south eastern Nigeria have suffered from serious time and cost overruns which have led to so many project abandonment and failure. It has resulted to multiplier effect on the economy of the country leading to colossal loss of scarce resources and poor infrastructural development. A typical example are flyover projects at Owerri, is the Onitsha-Enugu, and Enugu-Port Harcourt express ways which have been abandoned due to time and cost overruns. These problems could be attributed to certain factors which need to be identify and examined critically. For instance, significant considering the climatic condition, weather and environmental characteristics, usually challenge project success. For that reason, it is of key

(2007). In their own contributions. Choudhry (2004) and Chan (2004) define time overrun as the difference between the actual completion time and the estimated completion time. It was measured in number of days. Project delays cause the project completion date to be increased (Al-Gahtani Monan(2007). From above time overruns is defined as the time increased to complete the project after planned date which is caused by internal and external factors surrounding the project.

In some cases, time overrun problems usually result to project cost overrun Zhu et al (2004) refer to cost overrun as excess of actual cost over budget. Cost overrun is also sometimes called "cost increases", or "budget overrun". It is the change in contract amount divided by the original contract award amount. This calculation was converted to a percentage for ease of comparison by Jackson (2002)

important to detect the salient factors, treat all weakness points and from all sides give specific priorities in order to avoid time and cost overruns in construction projects.

The principal objectives of this study are to identity and analyse the factors influencing time and cost overruns on construction projects in south eastern Nigeria. The specific objectives include.

- ❖ To identify the variables influencing time and cost overruns in construction projects and to evaluate their relative importance.
- ❖ To examine the collective group perspectives on the relative significance of these factors from client, consultant and contractor points of view.
- ❖ To evaluate the degree of agreement/disagreement regarding the ranking of these factors.
- ❖ To proffer recommendations for improving performance index of

construction projects in the south eastern Nigeria.

The following research hypothesis was formulated for validity test.

HO₁: There is no significant degree of agreement among the clients, contractors and consultants in the level of influence between time and cost overruns in the management of construction projects.

The scope of this work is centered on factors influencing time and cost overruns on construction projects in the south east geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. The study covers four selected states in the region, which includes; Imo, Abia, Anambra and Enugu States. The study will be found useful by all the parties involved in construction projects which include clients, contractors and consultants. It would also ensure project managers are given their rightful place in construction projects.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Cost overruns in construction project management could be attributed to have been commonly unpredictable weather, inflation in material cost, inaccurate material's estimates, complexity of project, contractor's lack of geographical experience, contractor's lack of project type experience, and non-familiarity with local regulations, (Kaming et al 2007). Similarly, Morris (2006) mentioned ten factors influencing cost overruns in construction projects. These factors are inadequate project preparation, planning and implementation, delay in construction, supply of raw material and equipment by contractor, change in the scope of the project. resource constraints: funds, foreign exchange, power, associated auxiliaries not ready. The delay in decisions making by government, failure of specific coordination bodies, wrong/inappropriate choice of site, technical incompetence and poor organizational structure, labour unrest, natural calamities, restiveness, war and lack of experience of technical consultants,

inadequacy of design collaboration agreements, monopoly to technology. Jagboro (2005) also examine the factors influencing construction cost overruns on building projects in Nigeria. He found that cost overruns occur more frequently and are thus a more severe problem than time overruns in Nigeria. The predominant factors influencing cost overruns are materials cost increase due to inflation, inaccurate materials estimating and degree of project complexity. Frimpong et al (2004) identify and study 26 factors causing cost overrun in the construction of Ground Water Project in Ghana, they sent 55 questionnaires to clients, 40 to contractors and 30 to consultants. According to the contractors and consultants opinions, monthly payment difficulties from agencies was the most important cost overruns factor, while clients ranked poor contractor management as the most important factor. Despite some difference in viewpoints held by the three groups surveyed, there is a high degree of agreement among them with respect to their ranking of the factors. The overall ranking results indicate that the three groups felt that the major factors that can cause excessive groundwater project overruns in developing countries are poor contractor management, monthly payment difficulties from agencies, materials procurement, poor technical performance, escalation of material prices according to their degree of influences. The main types of delay have been stated by a number of researchers, Vidalis et al (2007), Ahmed et al (2007), Elinwa et al (2005) and Al-Gahtani and Mohan (2007), Ahmed et al (2009). These types are excusable delay, concurrent delay, compensable delay, and critical delay: The types of delays above have internal or external impacts on project process. Internal causes of delay include cases that come from the client designers, contractors, and consultants. External causes of delays are originated from outside of construction projects such as utility companies, government, subcontractors, suppliers, labour-unions etc.

Time overruns (delays) could be divided into three categories; according to sources (years) they are:

- ❖ Those over which neither party to the contract has any control;
- ❖ Those over which the client (or his/her representative) has control;
- ❖ Those over which the contractor (or any subcontractor) has control. In some countries, the predominant factors influencing time overrun are design changes, poor labour productivity, inadequately planning and resource shortages.

Ahmedetal (2009) posit that internal causes of delay include the causes arising from

four parties involved in the project. These parties include the client, designers, contractors and consultants. Other delays, which do not arise from these four parties, are based on external causes. Chan et al (2004), Ogunlana et al (2005), Kaming et al (2007) and Alwi et al (2002) mentioned the possible factors causing delays in construction projects: a number of researcher have categorized the factors that causes delays in the four categories, these are: consultant's responsibility, contractor's responsibilities, client responsibilities and external factors.

Table 1: Illustrates the factors causing time overruns

Category	Factors
Client	Finance and payment of completed work, Client interference, Slow decision-making by clients, Unrealistic imposed contract duration
Contractor	Subcontractors, Site management, Construction methods, Improper planning, Mistakes during construction, Inadequate contractor experience
Consultant	Contract management, Preparation and approval of drawings, Quality assurance/control, Waiting time for approval of test and inspections
Materials	Quality of material, Shortage in material
Labour and equipment	Labour supply, Labour productivity, Equipment availability and failure
Contractual relationships	Major disputes and negotiations, Inappropriate organizational structure linking parties, Lack of communication between the parties
External factors	Weather condition, Regulatory changes and building code,

	Unforeseen ground conditions, Political conditions, Economic conditions
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Source: Aibinu and Jagboro (2004).

LITERATURE REVIEW

The following list of factors could be attributed to cost overrun in a typical construction project according to Morris (2006).

Incomplete design at the time of tender, additional work at client’s request, changes in client’s brief, lack of cost planning/monitoring during pre- and post contract stages, site/poor soil conditions, adjustment of prime cost and provisional sums, re-measurement of provisional works, Logistics due to site location, lack of cost reports during construction stage.

Also list of other factors, which are usually ignored are:

Delays in issuing information to the contractor during construction, technical omissions at design stage, contractual claims, such as, extension of time with cost claims, improvements to standard

drawings during construction stage. indecision by the supervising team, in dealing with the contractor’s queries, delays in costing variation and additional works, omission and errors in the bills of quantities, ignoring items with abnormal rates during tender evaluation, especially items with provisional quantities, some tendering maneuvers by contractors, such as front-loading of rates.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted survey technique of research design with area and random sampling procedure. Data collection was through Primary source in which questionnaires and interviews were employed. Questionnaires were distributed to 124 respondents (66 contractors, 27 consultants and 31 clients) with one questionnaire to each respondent. A total of 151 questionnaires were distributed and 124 were returned.

Table 2: The population includes; contracting companies, consulting firms and clients

State	Contractors	Consultants	Clients
Imo	33	13	13
Abia	10	6	3
Anambra	6	3	4
Enugu	17	5	6

The sample size was determined by the equation.

$$SS = \frac{Z^2 \times P \times (1 - P)}{C^2} \dots\dots\dots 1$$

Where SS = Sample size

Z = Z value (eg 1.96 for 95% confidence level)

P = Percentage picking a choice, expressed as a decimal (0.50 used for sample size needed)

C = Margin of error (9%).

Correction for finite population could therefore be presented as:

$$SS_{new} = 1 + \frac{SS}{SS - 1} \dots\dots\dots 2$$

The methods of data analysis used in the study are spearman’s rank correlation coefficient (e) and Kendall’s coefficient of concordance (W). spearman’s rank correlation coefficient is use to test how close two sets of data are linked. It shows the extent of relationship existing between ranked variables of two population. The simple computational formula is

$$e = 1 - \frac{6 \sum_{i=1}^n d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)} \dots\dots\dots 3$$

Where d_i = the difference between the assigned ranks to x_i the rank assigned to y_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots\dots\dots n$; the sample size. Similarly, Kendall’s coefficient of concordance is an non-parametric test statistic for measure of relationship. It is a normalization of Friedman test statistic. It is used for assessing the level of agreement or closeness that exist between three or more populations W is used in determining the degree of association among several (K) sets of ranking of N objects or individuals. W is considered an appropriate measure of studying the degree of association among three or more sets of rankings.

Kendall’s coefficient of concordance $W = W = \frac{S}{\frac{1}{2}k^2(N^2 - N)} \dots\dots\dots 4$

Where $S = S = \sum R_j - \bar{R}_j)^2$

R_j – sum of the rank for each variable. \bar{R}_j = mean value of each variable ie; $\bar{R}_j = \frac{\sum R_j}{R_j}$. For judging

whether the calculated value of W is significantly different from zero depends on the size of N. If $N \leq 7$, a table usually given critical value of S association with W significance at 5% and 1% as $X^2 = k(N - 1)$. W with degree of freedom = (N – 1) for judging W’s significance at a given level in the usual way of using X^2 value. However, computer-based analyses were used with relevant softwares.

Table 3: Results of the Analysis Correlation test of “project group” among contractor, consultant and client

Group	Contractor and Client	P. value	Contractor and Consultant	P. value	Client and Consultant	P. value
	Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient	
Project	0.782	0.006*	0.804	0.004*	0.697	0.018*

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 significance level.

Table 4: Correlation test of “contractor’s” responsibility group among contractor, consultant and client.

Group	Contractor and Client	P. value	Contractor and Consultant	P. value	Client and Consultant	P. value
	Correlation		Correlation		Correlation	

	coefficient		coefficient		coefficient	
Contractor's responsibilities	0.544	0.004*	0.477	0.011*	0.456	0.014*

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 significance level

Table 5: Correlation test of consultant's responsibility group among contractor, consultant and client

Group	Contractor and Client	P. value	Contractor and Consultant	P. value	Client and Consultant	P. value
	Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient	
Consultant's responsibilities	0.649	.0008*	0.485	0.046*	0.538	0.029*

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 significance level

Table 6: Correlation test of client's responsibility group

Group	Contractor and Client	P. value	Contractor and Consultant	P. value	Client and Consultant	P. value
	Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient	
Client's responsibilities	0.363	0.169	0.384	0.154	0.623	0.037*

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 significance level

Table 7: Correlation test of professional management

Group	Contractor and Client	P. value	Contractor and Consultant	P. value	Client and Consultant	P. value
	Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient	
Contractor's responsibilities	0.021	0.476	-0.073	0.415	0.430	0.094

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 significance level

Table 8: Correlation test of design and documentation group

Group	Contractor and Client	P. value	Contractor and Consultant	P. value	Client and Consultant	P. value
	Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient	
Design and	0.759	0.014*	0.189	0.327	0.131	0.379

documentation						
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*Correlation is significant at 0.05 significance level

Table 9: Correlation test of “materials group” among contractor, consultant and client

Group	Contractor and Client	P. value	Contractor and Consultant	P. value	Client and Consultant	P. value
	Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient	
Materials	0.923	0.001*	0.457	0.128	0.499	0.104

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 significance level

Table 10: Correlation test of “execution group” among contractor, consultant and client

Group	Contractor and Client	P. value	Contractor and Consultant	P. value	Client and Consultant	P. value
	Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient	
Execution	0.836	0.010*	0.768	0.022*	0.871	0.005*

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 significance level

Table 11: Correlation test of “labour and equipment group” among contractor, consultant and client

Group	Contractor and Client	P. value	Contractor and Consultant	P. value	Client and Consultant	P. value
	Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient	
Labour and equipment	0.977	0.000*	0.438	0.119	0.482	0.095

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 significance level

Table 12: Correlation test of consultant’s responsibility group among contractor, consultant and client

Group	Contractor and Client	P. value	Contractor and Consultant	P. value	Client and Consultant	P. value
	Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient	
Consultant’s responsibilities	0.933	0.034*	0.998	0.001*	0.951	0.025*

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 significance level

Table 13: Correlation test of government relations group among contractor, consultant and client

Group	Contractor and Client	P. value	Contractor and Consultant	P. value	Client and Consultant	P. value
	Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient	
Government relations	-0.889	0.152	-0.926	0.124	0.649	0.275

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 significance level

Table 14: Correlation test of “External” group among contractor, consultant and client

Group	Contractor and Client	P. value	Contractor and Consultant	P. value	Client and Consultant	P. value
	Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient	
External factors	0.940	.0003*	0.921	0.005*	0.747	0.004*

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 significance level

Table 15: Correlation test of consultant’s responsibility group among contractor, consultant and client

Group	Contractor and Client	P. value	Contractor and Consultant	P. value	Client and Consultant	P. value
	Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient	
Time overrun	0.940	.0000*	0.421	0.000*	0.550	0.000*

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 significance level

Table 16: Correlation test of consultant’s responsibility group among contractor, consultant and client

Group	Contractor and Client	P. value	Contractor and Consultant	P. value	Client and Consultant	P. value
	Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient		Correlation coefficient	
Cost overruns	0.792	.0000*	0.737	0.000*	0.819	0.000*

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 significance level

Table 17: Kendall’s coefficient of concordance

#	Group	W	Chi-square	p-value	Decision
1.	Project	0.174	64.206	1.000	Don't reject Ho
2.	Contractor's responsibilities	0.379	139.851	0.142	Don't reject Ho
3.	Consultant's responsibilities	0.189	69.741	1.000	Don't reject Ho
4.	Client's responsibilities	0.127	46.863	1.000	Don't reject Ho
5.	Professional management	0.303	111.807	0.756	Don't reject Ho
6.	Design and documentation	0.179	66.051	1.000	Don't reject Ho
7.	Materials	0.536	197.784	0.000*	Reject Ho
8.	Execution	0.248	91.512	0.985	Don't reject Ho
9.	Labour and equipment	0.285	105.165	0.876	Don't reject Ho
10.	Contractual relationship	0.300	110.700	0.779	Don't reject Ho
11.	Government relations	0.135	49.815	1.000	Don't reject Ho
12.	External factors	0.419	154.611	0.028*	Reject Ho

	Overall influence on time overrun	0.333	122.877	0.486	Don't reject Ho
	Overall influence on cost overrun	0.362	133.578	0.243	Don't reject Ho
	Overall influence on time and cost overrun	0.346	127.674	0.368	Don't reject Ho

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULT

The p-value for the material group is 0.000 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$, we reject the null hypothesis and therefore conclude that there is sufficient evidence to support the alternative hypothesis, hence there is a degree of agreement amongst clients, contractors and consultants. The result have shown that client, contractors and consultants were in agreement that material group has much significant impact on delay of construction projects in South East Nigeria. The continuous fluctuation in the prices of raw materials for the construction industry (rapid escalation and moderate falls), importation of construction materials giving rise to uncontrollable hike in prices, shortage of construction materials in markets and sites have all contributed significantly to delays in construction projects. These are as a result of unstable economic situation, high tariffs imposed by the government and unstable dollar-naira value. Therefore getting the right mixes of construction materials at the appropriate time are the necessary ingredients that propel the standards needed in construction projects in Nigeria (Ogunlana et al 2005).

The P-value for the external factor group is 0.028 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is sufficient evidence to support the alternative hypothesis, hence there is a degree of agreement amongst clients, contractors and consultants. The result of the study also revealed that external factor group also contributed immensely to the delay in construction projects. Compensation fees paid to host communities, poor economic conditions, abduction/ kidnapping of foreign and local contractors, poor site condition, changes in laws and regulations, and weather condition. The parties to project were in agreement regarding these factors. External factors are often seen as reflex factors which make them difficult to control Jabgoro (2004).

For the groups of; project related, contractors responsibilities, consultants responsibilities, clients responsibilities, professional management, design and documentation, execution, Labour and equipment, contractual relationship and Government relations factors, their P-values were greater than $\alpha = 0.05$, then the null hypothesis is not rejected and we

therefore conclude that there is insufficient evidence to support the alternative hypothesis. Hence, there is no degree of agreement amongst the clients, contractors and consultants on the influence on construction projects in south eastern Nigeria. On the other hand, for the overall influence on time overrun, cost overrun and combination of time and cost overruns, their P-values were greater than $\alpha = 0.05$, therefore the null hypothesis is not rejected and there is insufficient evidence to support the alternative hypothesis. Hence, there is no degree of agreement amongst the clients, contractors and consultants regarding their influence on construction projects in south eastern Nigeria.

Conclusion

This work investigated an analysis of factors influencing time and cost overruns on construction projects in South East Nigeria. The test carried were aimed at ascertaining the factors that contributed immensely to delays in construction projects. Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was used for pair sample test to determine the level of significance regarding each pair of project parties. Furthermore, Kendall's coefficient of concordance was adopted to ascertain the degree in agreement amongst all the project parties. The result of the study has shown that materials and external related factors are indeed crucial factors causing delays on construction projects in South Eastern Nigeria.

The following recommendations are therefore proffered to guide in decision making. Contractors should be aware of the construction materials to use, so they are advised to purchase right quantity and quality of construction materials at the right time. The adoption of principles of material requirements planning is necessary to avoid shortages or surplus of materials. The stakeholders in construction project should desist from cutting corners in relation to

money meant for settling host communities before the start of work.

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